

Greedy Graph Coloring and Hungarian Algorithms for Resource Scheduling in TWDM-PONh

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Abstract—The time and wavelength division multiplexing passive optical network (TWDM-PON) allows numerous users to share a single optical fiber and wavelength. In TWDM-PON, the optical network unit (ONU) has different upstream and downstream user traffic to serve using a limited amount of optical resources. Dynamic wavelength and time slot scheduling play an important role in managing user traffic variation. As is well known, delay is one of the most important performance parameters of TWDM-PON. This motivates us to investigate the delay optimization problem and solve it through resource scheduling. To optimize delay performance, we propose a greedy graph coloring algorithm (GGCA) to dynamically assign the timeslots for upstream packet transmissions. Moreover, we also propose a Hungarian algorithm (HA) to solve the wavelength scheduling problem within the scheduled timeslots by the GGCA. Numerical simulations show that the proposed GGCA and HA provide approximately 70- 80% delay reduction compared to a fixed baseline algorithm that schedules the timeslots and the wavelength in a fixed manner.

Index Terms—Delay optimization, greedy graph coloring algorithm, Hungarian algorithm, resource scheduling, time and wavelength division multiplexing passive optical network.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, midhaul and backhaul are highly dependent on passive optical networks (PON) that use point-to-multi-point fiber from the optical line terminal (OLT) to the end user premises [1]. The cost-effective deployment of PON shows scalable, flexible, and higher bandwidths allowing us to deploy optical and radio converge solutions with lower signaling loss at the midhaul and backhaul of mobile wireless networks. Several research works are conducted to prove that the PON is a highly capable access network that effectively converges several service providers (e.g., collecting data from multiple sensor networks and seamless connectivity in multiple end users) without suffering from any bandwidth deficiency [2]. The rapidly increasing demand for data from a wide range of

novel use cases and applications is pushing the evolution of the technological enablers to provide unprecedented levels of performance in terms of capacity, delay, reliability, robustness, security, and automation [3], [5]–[8]. The advantage of Time Division Multiplexing Passive Optical Network (TDM-PON) is that it allows numerous users to share a single optical fiber and wavelength [4], whereby each subscriber is assigned a distinct timeslot for data transmission and detection. The time wavelength division multiplexing PON (TWDM-PON) is used to improve the system capacity of other PON solutions, typically providing wavelengths for data transmission. In TWDM-PON, optimally scheduling the resources is much more complex and challenging in order to improve performance and satisfy the demands of the underlying users. Therefore, several research works have already addressed the problem of resource scheduling to optimize the performance of TWDM-PON [9], [10], [12], [14], [15], [17]. However, joint resource scheduling problems to minimize upstream packet delay by optimal assignments timeslots and wavelengths are out of the scope in the above mentioned papers. This motivates us to solve joint resource scheduling problems to minimize the packet delay of TWDM-PON. In this paper, we propose a low-complexity greedy graph coloring and Hungarian algorithm to solve the timeslots and the wavelength scheduling problems in TWDM-PON.

A. PRIOR RELATED WORKS

The bandwidth allocation scheme has a huge impact on the upstream delay which has become a major challenge for the optical segment in an optical and radio converged architecture (ORCA). In [9], a machine learning-driven dynamic bandwidth allocation scheme is proposed to optimize bandwidth allocation decisions to satisfy uplink latency requirements. Similarly, a bandwidth scheduling problem is considered in [10] and proposes an interleaved polling method to evaluate average packet delay performance with different loads in TWDM-PON architecture. Similarly, the bandwidth allocation is studied in [11] to enhance the efficiency of the unused bandwidth and propose a dual-polling dynamic bandwidth allocation (DBA) method to evaluate the delay performance of elastic PON. In [12], an optimal upstream bandwidth and wavelength scheduling algorithm are proposed to evaluate the end-to-end delay performance by minimizing the number of active wavelength channels. In [13], a DBA algorithm is proposed where a statistical approach considers bandwidth allocation that increases the spectral efficiency while allocating the services to the occupied channels. Similarly, the

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TABLE I
STATE-OF-THE-ART (SOTA) SUMMARY OF RESOURCE SCHEDULING PON.

Reference	Year	Bandwidth scheduling problem	Wavelength scheduling problem	Timeslots scheduling problem	Packet delay evaluation
[8]	2016	Not solved	Solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[9]	2023	Solved	Not solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[10]	2015	Solved	Not solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[11]	2015	Solved	Not solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[12]	2019	Solved	Solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[13]	2022	Solved	Not solved	Not solved	Not Evaluated
[14]	2009	Not solved	Solved	Not solved	Not Evaluated
[15]	2021	Solved	Solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[16]	2020	Solved	Not solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[17]	2024	Solved	Solved	Not solved	Not Evaluated
[18]	2023	Solved	Solved	Not solved	Not Evaluated
[19]	2022	Solved	Not solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[20]	2024	Solved	Solved	Not solved	Evaluated
[21]	2023	Solved	Not solved	solved	Evaluated
[22]	2024	Not solved	solved	solved	Evaluated
Our current paper	2024	Not solved	Solved	Solved	Evaluated

wavelength allocation has a significant impact on improving the performance of the optical segment in ORCA. Therefore, several research studies are conducted to solve the wavelength allocation problem to improve the performance of the optical segment on the architecture.

In TWDM-PON, low-latency requirements and scheduling a certain amount of wavelengths are very critical to satisfy the demands of the users. Therefore, the authors in [14] solved the wavelengths scheduling problem and proposed a priority-based greedy heuristic algorithm to minimize deployment cost while satisfying the users demands in the networks. In [15], a sleep-aware wavelength and bandwidth assignment scheme is proposed for TWDM-PON to allocate the bandwidth and wavelengths to all the ONUs to minimize the upstream packet delay. The fronthaul delay performance is evaluated by Datsik *et al.* [16] to provide an impact of different functional split types in a radio-over-fibre (RoF) architecture. A joint wavelength and bandwidth allocation algorithm is studied in [17] to significantly enhance the efficiency of wavelength and bandwidth utilization of TWDM-PON. In addition, a dynamic wavelength and bandwidth allocation is proposed in [18] to minimize the frame rearrangement issue of next-generation elastic PON architecture. Dynamic joint functional split and resource allocation optimization problem is solved in [19] to facilitate the service delivery and reduce the power consumption in the elastic optical fronthaul. Similarly, multiple functional splitting options over TWDM-EPON are studied by Ciceri *et al.* in [20] that distribute the resources amongst ONUs serving functional split options based on their bandwidth and latency requirements in networks. The simulation results prove that the proposed scheme provides better utilization of the resources by meeting the delay requirements of the dedicated fronthaul splits.

The upstream packets in a TWDM-PON architecture are simultaneously generated by the users and transmitting the packets by the ONUs towards OLT requires congestion avoidance transmissions. Therefore, the timeslots are needed to be optimally assigned by the OLT based on satisfying the demands of the users. To this regard, the authors in [21] proposed an integer linear programming scheduling model

and a greedy-based time slot equalization heuristic scheduling algorithm to improve the scheduling decisions and reduce the average delay of the time-sensitive traffic flow in a TDM-PON architecture. However, a dynamic wavelength scheduling and time slot assignment algorithm for TWDM-PON is proposed by Tang *et al.* in [22] based on considering rating mechanisms amongst the ONUs and through simulation results the authors show that the time delay and packet loss ratio are reduced compared with conventional methods. The summary of the prior related works for resource scheduling in TWDM-PON is listed in Table I.

B. MAIN CONTRIBUTIONS

The above work triggers an appealing observation that bandwidth, wavelengths, and timeslot scheduling lead to enhancing the performance of any PON architecture. The purpose of resource scheduling in PON is to efficiently allocate the bandwidth and wavelengths to ensure reliable packet transmissions. The existing works on resource scheduling (e.g., bandwidth, wavelengths, and timeslots) have been studied either separately or jointly to evaluate the performance in terms of energy saving, average delay, upstream delay, energy consumption, granted data length, spectral efficiency, minimization of number of deployed fibers, bandwidth waste, bandwidth and wavelength utilization, resource utilization efficiency, and packet loss rate for different PON architecture [8]–[22].

To the best of our knowledge, no prior research has been conducted to reduce the packet delay by jointly scheduling the resources and timeslots in a TWDM-PON architecture. Therefore, in this paper, we propose a resource scheduling algorithm in an optical and radio converged architecture to solve the timeslots and wavelength scheduling problems dynamically to evaluate the delay performance of TWDM-PON architecture. The key contributions of the paper are listed below:

- Firstly, we define a joint optimization problem of timeslots and wavelength scheduling in a TWDM-PON architecture. We solve the problem in a dynamic manner while satisfying all the constraints that handle the different demands of ONUs with various locations

- Secondly, we propose two heuristic algorithms to solve the timeslots and wavelength scheduling problems. The timeslot assignment (TSA) problem is solved by our proposed greedy graph coloring algorithm (GGCA) and we further propose a Hungarian algorithm [23] to optimally schedule the wavelengths within the assigned timeslots.
- Finally, we evaluate the delay performance of the proposed GGCA and Hungarian algorithm and compare the performance with a fixed resource scheduling algorithm [24]. It is illustrated through numerical simulation that our proposed algorithms provide approximately 80% lower latency than the baseline algorithm (e.g. fixed resource allocation).

In this subsection, we listed the variables used in formulating the proposed scheme, such as the packet delay End-to-End (D_{E2E}), number of ONUs (M), number of timeslots (N), number of wavelengths (W), demands of ONUs (d_i), capacity of wavelength (R_w), maximum distance between OLT and ONUs (L_i), threshold of far distance (L_{max}), speed of light propagates in optical fiber (v), delay threshold of fronthaul streams (γ), timeslots length (δ), traffic threshold (B_{min}), the allocation state of ONU_i for $Time_Slot_j$ which is the decision variable (x_{it}) and the allocation state of ONU_i for $wavelength_w$ which is the decision variable (y_{iw}),

The structure of the paper is organized as follows: firstly, we describe the TWDM-PON system model that is considered. Secondly, we introduce the research problem and the related constraints stated in Section II. The optimization algorithms are described in Section III. Section IV presents the simulation results. Finally, the paper concludes in Section V with possible future research directions.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we describe the system model and the definition of the problem. The proposed system model consists of an optical line terminal (OLT), a wavelength multiplexer, and a number of optical network units (ONUs). The ONUs are connected with the splitters and the splitters can be deployed in star networks with a split ratio of 1:M. We provide a brief description of the system model architecture in the next subsection of the paper.

We consider a system model as shown in Fig. 1 comprised of M number of ONUs geographically distributed randomly within 1-40 Km from the OLT. In this paper, we solve the problem of resource scheduling in upstream directing with varying demands at the ONUs and minimize the packet delay of transmission. We assume two types of delay to formulate the problem, i.e., the propagation delay based on the distance between the OLT and the corresponding ONUs and the actual transmission delay of the packets. We further divided the M number of ONUs into 3 different clusters to vary the propagation delay. Moreover, we generate the traffic for M number of ONUs based on uniform distribution and we classify the demands into 2 categories. The lightweight demands of the ONUs are expected to utilize less amount of wavelength and timeslots to transmit the packets. On the

contrary, the high-demand traffic will utilize more resources and timeslots. Therefore, we propose two algorithms in this paper that dynamically solve the optimization problem.

We consider four pairs of wavelengths for upstream as used in [25] that are multiplexed using a wavelength division multiplexed multiplexer. Such a system provides a total capacity of at least 40 Gb/s for the upstream direction, with 10 Gbps carried by each wavelength. Each ONU transmits on one of the upstream wavelengths allocated to it based on our proposed Hungarian algorithm. Furthermore, we also solve the timeslot scheduling problem where an ONU transmits data only within the scheduled timeslots to minimize the total delay and avoid collision of the packets in the network. The OLT receives the upstream packets from each ONU in a burst manner based on allocated timeslots. The physical distance from ONUs to an OLT varies, and the distance variation provides significant variation in the propagation delay between the ONUs and OLT. To formulate the problem, we consider the propagation delay and the transmission delay and also assume that each ONU has bursts of generated traffic upstream. In the following subsection of the paper, we are briefly providing the definition of the propagation and transmission delays.

We formulate a joint resource scheduling problem that minimizes packet delay of a TWDM-PON architecture. The joint optimization problem of allocating timeslots and wavelength scheduling problems are solved dynamically to minimize the packet delay while satisfying several constraints of the problem. The joint optimization problem (OP) can be formulated as follows:

$$\mathbf{OP} : \min_{x_{it}, y_{iw}} \sum_{i=1}^M \left[\left(\frac{L_i}{v} + \frac{M d_i}{\sum_{t=1}^T x_{it} \sum_{w=1}^W y_{iw} R_w} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

The proposed algorithms are subjected to the following optimization constraints (OC):

$$\mathbf{OC1} : \sum_{t=1}^N x_{it} \geq 1; \quad ; \quad \forall i, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{OC2} : \sum_{w=1}^W y_{iw} \geq 1; \quad ; \quad \forall i, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{OC3} : \sum_{w=1}^W y_{iw} R_w \geq d_i \quad ; \quad \forall i, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{OC4} : \sum_{i=1}^M y_{iw} x_{it} \leq 1 \quad \forall w, t, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{OC5} : D_{E2E} \leq \gamma \quad \forall i, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{OC6} : x_{it} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{OC7} : y_{iw} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (8)$$

where the **OC1** in (2) represents the timeslot allocation, where each ONU_i must be assigned at least one timeslot to transmit packets from ONU to OLT. The **OC2** in (3), **OC3** in (4), and **OC4** in (5), **OC5** in (6) are the wavelength allocation constraint to ensure that the ONU_i can be assigned one or more wavelengths, guaranteeing the demand satisfaction,

Fig. 1. Proposed system model.

guaranteeing collision avoidance where two ONUs are not allocated the same wavelength within the same timeslot, guaranteeing that the packet delay does not exceed maximum threshold, respectively. The delay threshold is considered in (5) to satisfy the quality-of-service (QoS) of any delay-sensitive services in TWDM-PON. We also consider **OC6** in (7) to define a binary variable indicating whether ONU i is assigned to timeslots t , then $x_{it} = 1$, otherwise, $x_{it} = 0$. Similarly, the **OC7** in (8) is used to define a binary variable indicating whether ONU i is assigned to wavelength w , then $y_{iw} = 1$, otherwise $y_{iw} = 0$. To solve the **OP** in (1) we propose two heuristic algorithms that are briefly described next section of this paper. Eq (1) represents an integer problem (0/1) with a non-convex structure, making it challenging to solve using traditional algorithms. Traditional methods require converting the problem into a convex form, which is computationally expensive and not scalable for large instances. Instead, heuristic algorithms are preferred because they provide a simpler, faster, and more practical approach to finding near-optimal solutions while efficiently handling the complexity of the problem.

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

This section proposes two novel heuristic algorithms to reduce the packet transmission time and improve the efficiency of the resource scheduling process. This paper section describes our proposed algorithms that solve the timeslots and wavelength allocation problem of TWDM-PON architecture. The flowchart of the proposed algorithms is shown in Fig. 3 where the timeslots assignment (TSA) problem is solved by using the proposed greedy graph coloring algorithm (GGCA) and within the assigned timeslots, the proposed Hungarian Algorithm solves wavelength allocation problem. In the following subsection of the paper, we briefly describe the procedures of both our algorithms with dedicated examples.

Fig. 2. An example of TS allocation of the proposed GGCA.

A. THE PROPOSED GREEDY GRAPH COLORING ALGORITHM

In this paper, we proposed a greedy graph coloring algorithm (GGCA) to solve the timeslots (TS) assignment problem in TWDM-PON architecture. In the proposed GGCA, we assume a bipartite graph (BG) in which vertices are represented by two sets with a number of nodes. The edge of

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the proposed GGCA and HAWA algorithms.

the BG represents the TS assignment for the ONUs. The ONUs with the assigned TS will transmit the packets based on the wavelength allocated by our other proposed Hungarian algorithm discussed in the next section of the paper. In the paper, we provide an example of our proposed GGCA in Fig. 2 where N number of TS are assigned to M number of ONUs. As can be seen from Fig. 2, if the ONU_1 is already assigned to the timeslots t_1 , the assigned TS can be shared with other ONUs with different wavelength to avoid collision of the packets. We can also observe from Fig. 1 that multiple ONUs can be served with different assigned wavelengths within the same timeslots. The pseudocode of the proposed GGCA is provided in Algorithm 1. As shown in Fig. 3, the proposed GGCA solves the TS assignment problem within five key steps. The procedure of the steps are described as follows:

- **Initialization:** In this step, the decision variable x_{it} , is initialized as a matrix with all zeros. The matrix's dimension is equivalent to the number of ONUs and timeslots, respectively.
- **Classification:** In this step of the GGCA, we assume that the upstream demands of the traffic are uniformly distributed and it is classified into two levels. The traf-

fic levels are determined based on a threshold B_{min} [25]. The traffic received at the ONUs is classified as lightweight when it lies lower than the threshold B_{min} value. On the contrary, traffic higher than the threshold is considered to be in high demand. This paper assumes lightweight traffic requires fewer timeslots to serve it with lower wavelength utilization.

- **Assignment:** In this step of GGCA, the timeslots are allocated to the number of ONUs based on the classified traffic demands.
- **Constraints violation:** At this step, we check the optimization constraint in Eq. (2) and confirm that at least a single timeslot is allocated for all the ONUs.
- **Returning:** At the last step of GGCA, we will receive an optimal allocation of the timeslots assignment x_{it} needed for the upstream packet transmission.

B. THE PROPOSED HUNGARIAN ALGORITHM FOR WAVELENGTH ALLOCATION

In this paper, we propose to use the Hungarian algorithm that optimally schedules the wavelengths to the ONUs within the timeslots assigned by the GGCA. The Hungarian algorithm

Algorithm 1 The Proposed GGCA for TS Assignment

- 1: **Start**
- 2: **Input:** $M, N, d_i, L_i, B_{min}, \delta$
- 3: **Output:** x_{it}
- 4: **Initialization:** Initialize the assignment matrix of the timeslot assignment x_{it}
- 5: **Initialization:** Initialize two lists to store the ONU_s with heavy and light traffic
- 6: **Set FOR** loop for ONU increment $i = i + 1$
- 7: **if** $d_i > B_{min}$ and $L_i > L_{max}$
- 8: **Set** heavy demand list $\leftarrow ONU_i$
- 9: **else** light demand list $\leftarrow ONU_i$
- 10: **Calculate** needed timeslots for the current position and need of ONU_s
- 11: **Set FOR** loop for timeslots increment $t = t + 1$
- 12: **Assigning** assign the timeslots and Set $x_{it} = 1$
- 13: **Set** the timeslot assignment constraint of equation (2)
- 14: **Return** the optimal timeslots assignment x_{it}

Fig. 4. An example of the proposed Hungarian algorithm.

is a combinatorial optimization algorithm that solves the wavelength assignment problem in polynomial time. The time complexity of the HAWA is $\mathcal{O}(M^3)$, where M is the number of ONUs. We search again for the next smallest number of zeros and make the assignment until we assign all the existing wavelengths in this timeslot. The HAWA algorithm minimizes the objective function, i.e., the upstream packet delay of TWDM-PON architecture. Consequently, we first initialize the cost matrix where each element represents the assignment of wavelength to ONU_i . The pseudocode of the proposed HAWA algorithm is provided in Algorithm 2. In the paper, we provide an example of our proposed HAWA in Fig.

Algorithm 2 The proposed HAWA Algorithm

- 1: **Start**
- 2: **Input:** M, W, L_i, x_{it} , and d_i
- 3: **Output:** y_{iw}
- 4: **Initialization:** Initialize the cost matrix
- 5: **Row Reduction:** Row-wise searching and subtracting smallest element
- 6: **Column Reduction:** Column-wise searching and subtracting smallest element
- 7: **Covering Zeros:** Find the row or column with the highest number of zeros
- 8: **If** zeros in row $>$ zeros in column do:
- 9: **Updating list:** Find and cover a row with highest value
- 10: **Else**
- 11: **Updating list:** Find and cover a column with highest value
- 12: **Optimality checking:** Check the number of lines with the length of the matrix
- 13: **If** the Number of lines is equal to the length of the matrix
- 14: **Assignment:** Find the minimum number of zeros in a row and column (i.e., Assign that row and column)
- 15: **Else**
- 16: **Matrix adjustment:** Search for the uncovered smallest element in the matrix, subtract it from all uncovered elements, add it to the cross-elements, and re-check the optimality again.
- 17: **Return** the optimal assignment of ONU_s to wavelengths within each timeslot y_{iw}

4 where the assignment procedure is proposed. Within each timeslot, OLT can assign four different wavelengths to the ONUs based on their demands. For example, if the ONU_1 is already assigned to the timeslot t_0 , it can have one or more wavelengths in that allocated timeslot, whereas another ONU can have other wavelengths in the same timeslot. However, we can also observe from Fig.4 that no two ONUs can be assigned to the same wavelength within the same timeslot, to avoid packet collision. As shown in Fig.3, the proposed HAWA, solves the wavelength scheduling problem in several steps. The procedures of this algorithm are described in brief as follows:

- **Initialization:** At the beginning of the HAWA algorithm, the cost matrix (i.e., the packet delay in our case) is initialized with the number of ONUs and wavelength with the propagation delay for the ONUs.
- **Row-wise reduction:** In this step, we search for the smallest element in each row of the matrix and subtract it from other elements of the matrix
- **Column-wise reduction:** After performing the row-wise reduction on the matrix, we search for the smallest element in each column of the matrix and subtract it from other elements of the column
- **Covering zeros:** In this step, we cover all zeros in the matrix with the minimum number possible of lines
- **Updating list:** In the updating list step, we search for the largest number of zeros either in rows or columns and then cover that row or column that contains the largest

number of zeros and repeat this step until we cover all zeros in the matrix

- **Optimality checking:** After covering all zeros, we check the optimal solution before performing the assignment step. In this step of optimality check, if the length of the matrix or length of rows is equal to the existing lines, then we trigger the assignment step. Otherwise, we go to the matrix adjustment step.
- **Matrix adjustment:** In this step of the HAWA algorithm, if the optimal solution is not reached, we further search for the smallest element from all the entries of the uncovered elements (not covered by the lines) of the matrix obtained from previous steps. Subtract this smallest element from other uncovered elements and add it to the cross-point elements (i.e., the elements already covered by the line and the column) and Leave all other elements as they are. After the matrix adjustment step, we repeat the HAWA algorithm from the covering zeros step until enough rows and columns are crossed out and have enough zeros in the matrix for optimum matching (until we reach the optimal solution).
- **Assignment:** In the assignment step, we perform the allocation of the wavelengths to the ONUs within the allocated timeslots by the GGCA. To provide an optimal allocation of wavelengths, we search for the location of the smallest number of zeros, either in rows or columns, and then assign this row to the column (i.e., allocating the wavelength to the ONU corresponding to the selected timeslots).
- **Checking constraints:** At the constraint checking step, we check the wavelength assignment constraint to ensure that each ONU has at least one wavelength to send its own traffic.
- **Returning:** Finally, the algorithm will return the assignment of wavelengths to the ONUs representing the decision variable y_{iw} .

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we provide simulation results to illustrate the benefits of the proposed GGCA and HAWA algorithms that minimize the delay of TWDM-PON architecture. In this paper, we use uniform distribution to generate traffic for each ONU [15]. Each packet is byte-sized, and the total demands of each ONU are measured as the total size of the generated packets. We ensure that the total generated traffic does not exceed the buffer size. To provide the effectiveness of the proposed GGCA and HAWA, we compare average delay performance with 3 different combinations of the algorithms. In addition, the performance comparison between the GGCA and HAWA schemes we proposed and the traditional resource allocation scheme [26] that is used to allocate the timeslot and wavelengths in a fixed way (i.e., in a round-robin manner) is shown in this section. In this paper, the fixed timeslot allocation (FTA) and the fixed wavelength allocation (FWA) algorithms are considered baseline comparison methods that show lower performance in all the simulation settings. In TWDM-PON architecture, the resource scheduling mechanisms are dynamic in nature which can enhance the delay

TABLE II
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Notation	Description	Value
M	Number of ONUs range	4-32
N	Number of timeslots	2-10
W	Number of wavelengths	4
d_i	Demand of ONU_i range	[20-200]
R_w	Capacity of $wavelength_w$	10 Gbps
L_i	Distance between ONU_i and the OLT	up to 40 km
L_{max}	Threshold for far distance	30 km
v	Speed of light propagates in optical fiber	$2 \cdot 10^8$ m/s
γ	Delay threshold	250 μ s
δ	timeslot length	15625 bytes
B_{min}	Traffic threshold	24.876 kbyte
--	Packet length	500-1100 bytes

performance. Consequently, we also provide such dynamic behavior based on showing the delay performance by considering fixing timeslot allocation or wavelength allocation with our proposed GGCA and HAWA algorithms. We introduce several simulation algorithms for comparison to provide the robustness of our proposed algorithms. We define such algorithms as the proposed GGCA with FWA to see the behavior of the delay using the graph coloring algorithm, and FTA with HAWA to ensure the effectiveness of the Hungarian algorithm. We consider tree topology-based PON architecture with one OLT and M ONUs. A TWDM-PON fronthaul network with four wavelengths is considered. The capacity of each wavelength is 10 Gbps. Unless stated otherwise, simulation parameters for the proposed GGCA and HAWA algorithm are presented in Table II.

Fig. 5. Average packet delay with varying different numbers of ONUs.

Fig. 5 shows the average delay performance of the proposed and other algorithms versus the number of ONUs while other simulation parameters have fixed values, e.g., $N=2$, $d_i = 20-200$ packets [10], Packet length = 1000, respectively. As can be illustrated from Fig. 5 the average delay of all the algorithms increases as the number of ONUs increases. This is because the network load increases and more resources are needed to satisfy more demands; thus, this will introduce more delay in transmitting the packets. It can be observed from Fig. 5 that at about 8 ONUs, the average packet delay of the (FTA+FWA) and (GGCA+FWA) schemes rises quickly. The proposed (GGCA+HAWA) algorithms have significantly reduced the packet delay compared to the traditional algorithm. We also provide the performance of GGCA, with FWA and

Fig. 6. Average packet delay with varying numbers of timeslots.

the delay is increasing because there are not enough wavelengths to be assigned to ONUs to carry out their packets. In the case of using our proposed algorithm for wavelength assignment with an FTA (i.e., FTA with HAWA), there is a reduction in packet delay performance due to the fact that more wavelengths are allocated to carry out the packets from the ONUs. The baseline FTA and HAWA show more delayed performance due to not allocating the resources dynamically. On the contrary, the proposed GGCA and HAWA allocate the resources based on the needs of the demand in the network.

Fig. 6 illustrates the average delay performance of the proposed and other algorithms with varying numbers of timeslots while other simulation parameters have fixed values, e.g., $M=16$, $d_i = 20-200$ packets, Packet length = 1000, respectively. As can be shown from Fig. 6 the average delay of all the algorithms decreases as the number of timeslots increases. This is because the ONUs have much more flexibility to send the packets by all the resource scheduling algorithms. The proposed (GGCA+HAWA) algorithm shows lower delay performance than the other simulation scenarios where FTA and FWA are used to allocate the timeslot and schedule wavelength. In contrast, in the other scenarios (e.g., GGCA+FWA and FTA+HAWA), the delay performance is much lower than the case when both timeslots and wavelengths are scheduled in a fixed manner. In the first scenario (GGCA+FWA), the timeslots are assigned to ONUs based on the demands and only one wavelength per each assigned timeslot is allocated to satisfy the demands. Therefore, some of the ONUs will face higher delays due to not having enough wavelengths to carry out the packets. Similarly, in the second scenario (FTA+HAWA), the operation procedures are exactly opposite to the first scenario where many more wavelengths can be available to carry out the packets leads better performance than the first scenario. In the case of FTA with FWA, the average delay performance is very high due to not having a dynamic allocation of resources.

Fig. 7 illustrates the average delay performance of the proposed and other algorithms with varying sizes of the packets while other simulation parameters have fixed values, e.g., $M=16$, $N=2$ and $d_i = 20-200$ packets, respectively. In Fig. 9, we can observe that our proposed GGCA+HAWA reduces delay by 80% in comparison to the baseline algorithm, while HAWA can save 60% delay compared with the fixed algorithm and GGCA can reduce the delay up to 25% compared with the

Fig. 7. Average packet delay for different packet sizes.

fixed algorithm in the worst case (i.e. when the packet length is high). Thus, resource allocation from GGCA and HAWA for timeslots and wavelength assignment can both perform better than static ones which verifies the superiority of “resource scheduling dynamically” on other listed scheduling algorithms.

As can be shown from Fig. 7 the average delay of all the algorithms increases as the size of packets increases. This means that ONUs have more bits to send; thus, more resources are needed to reduce the delay. The proposed (GGCA+HAWA) algorithm shows lower delay performance than the other simulation scenarios where FTA and FWA are used to allocate the timeslot and schedule wavelength. In contrast, in the other scenarios (e.g., GGCA+FWA and FTA+HAWA), the delay performance is much lower than the case when both timeslots and wavelengths are scheduled in a fixed manner. In the first scenario (GGCA+FWA), the timeslots are assigned to ONUs based on the demands and only one wavelength per each assigned timeslot is allocated to satisfy the demands. Therefore, some of the ONUs will face higher delays when their packets are larger and they need more wavelengths to send their packets and due to not having enough wavelengths to carry out the packets, the delay will be increasing. Similarly, in the second scenario (FTA+HAWA), the operation procedures are exactly opposite from the first scenario where many more wavelengths can be available to carry out the packets leads better performance than the first scenario. In the case of FTA with FWA, the average delay performance is increasing significantly much more than all other scenarios, due to not having a dynamic allocation of resources so the assigned process may not entirely fill the needs of ONUs.

Fig. 8 illustrates the average delay performance of the proposed and other algorithms with varying distance ranges between OLT and ONUs while other simulation parameters have fixed values, e.g., $M=16$, $N=2$ and $d_i = 20-200$ packets, and Packet length = 1000, respectively. As shown in Fig. 8, the delay generally increases slightly when the distance increases. This is because the ONUs far from OLT will need more time to send their traffic, otherwise more delays will occur. The proposed (GGCA+HAWA) algorithm shows lower delay performance than the other simulation scenarios where FTA and FWA are used to allocate the timeslot and schedule wavelength. Moreover, the performance difference between

Fig. 8. Average packet delay for different ranges of OLT-ONU distance.

our proposed algorithm's different ranges of distances is not significantly increasing because far ONUs will have more resources to avoid increased delay. In contrast, in the other scenarios (e.g., GGCA+FWA and FTA+HAWA), the delay performance is much worse for the case when both timeslots and wavelengths are allocated in a fixed manner. In the first scenario (GGCA+FWA), we don't observe a significant increment in the delay performance. This is because far ONUs have enough timeslots allocated by our proposed GGCA algorithm so better performance is achieved. Similarly, in the second scenario (FTA+HAWA), there is little increment in the delay for far ONUs. This is because some ONUs will not have sufficient timeslots to send their packets. In the case of FTA with FWA, the average delay performance is very high due to not having a dynamic allocation of resources. For far ONUs, there will be a higher delay. In some cases, the delay is decreasing due to light demands under ONU uniform traffic load conditions, so ONUs do not need more resources, so less delay is achieved.

The results can be summarized as follows:

- As the number of ONUs increases, the average delay rises for all algorithms due to higher network load and resource demand. The proposed GGCA+HAWA algorithm significantly reduces delay compared to others by dynamically allocating resources based on demand, outperforming static approaches like FTA and FWA. (see Fig. 5).
- Increasing the number of timeslots decreases the average delay because ONUs gain greater flexibility to send packets. The GGCA+HAWA algorithm outperforms others by efficiently scheduling both timeslots and wavelengths, avoiding bottlenecks faced by static allocation schemes. (see Fig. 6)
- Larger packets increase average delay across all algorithms as more resources are required for transmission. The proposed GGCA+HAWA algorithm reduces delay by up to 80% compared to the baseline algorithm, demonstrating the benefits of dynamic resource allocation for handling varying packet sizes. (see Fig. 7)
- Average delay slightly increases with greater distance because of increased propagation time. The GGCA+HAWA algorithm mitigates delays even at longer distances by dynamically allocating resources to distant ONUs, maintaining superior performance compared to static methods.

(see Fig. 8)

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has investigated packet delay minimization of TWDM-PON through joint optimization of timeslot and wavelength. Two novel algorithms, i.e., GGCA and HAWA have been proposed to solve the timeslots and wavelengths scheduling problems. The proposed GGCA and HAWA algorithms utilize the resources efficiently and adaptively schedule the resources based on user demands. Consequently, the resource utilization of TWDM-PON is improved leading to further reduction of the packet delay performance. In all simulated scenarios, the proposed GGCA+HAWA algorithm demonstrates superior performance, achieving up to 70-80% lower packet delay than baseline static approaches. In our future work, we will investigate the possibility of further improving the algorithm's performance by incorporating the prediction of service demands using a machine learning approach.

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Sandra Arnaout: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing - Original Draft. Md Arifur Rahman: Supervision, Writing - Review and editing, Methodology, Validation. Md Munjure Mowla: Conceptualization, Writing - Review and editing. Sławomir Hausman: Writing - Review and editing. Piotr Korbel: Writing - Review and editing.

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